

A0506

Multiscale and Multiphysics Simulation Framework for Alkaline Electrolyzer Stacks

Anoop Narayanan (1), Kresten Juel Jensen (1), Thomas Bisgaard (1), Jonathan Dallaire* (1), Priit Priimägi (2), Rainer Küngas (2)

(1) Resolvent Denmark P/S, Måløv/Denmark;

(2) OÜ Stargate Hydrogen Solutions, Tallinn/Estonia;

*Contact corresponding authors: www.EFCF.com/ContactRequest

Abstract

Alkaline water electrolysis is a key technology for sustainable hydrogen production, yet their large-scale deployment is hindered by challenges in performance optimization and design scalability. To address these challenges, a multiscale and Multiphysics simulation framework is developed, which integrates reduced-order modeling (ROM) to analyze and optimize electrolyzer stacks at the cell and stack scales. The framework, implemented using COMSOL Multiphysics®, captures the coupled physics governing electrochemical reactions and fluid dynamics at different scales.

At the cell scale, a multiphase computational fluid dynamics (CFD) model is used to describe the flow distribution and pressure drop in the hydrogen and oxygen half-cells. A simplified stack CFD model represented by a reduced order model of each half-cell provides insights on flow distribution to all cells in the stack, as well as gas and liquid distribution in the stack manifolds. At the stack scale, the model evaluates electrochemical interactions to identify design and operational improvements.

The proposed framework is demonstrated on a commercial-scale stack containing 7 cells of diameter 0.35-meter, thereby enabling rapid evaluation of design alternatives and performance scenarios, facilitating iterative optimization with reduced computational costs. By bridging detailed physical insights with practical design applications, the framework supports the accelerated development and upscaling of alkaline electrolyzer stacks, ultimately contributing to more efficient and cost-effective hydrogen production systems.

Conceptual representation of the simulation framework

1. Introduction

Hydrogen production via renewable energy-powered electrolysis is a cornerstone of decarbonization strategies in heavy industries and long-range transportation. Among the various electrolysis technologies, alkaline water electrolysis (AWE) offers a mature and cost-effective route for green hydrogen generation. However, challenges related to performance optimization, stack uniformity, and scalability continue to limit its widespread adoption at industrial scales.

In particular, achieving uniform flow and electrochemical behavior across a stack remains non-trivial. High-fidelity modeling of multiphase flows, gas-liquid interactions, and electrochemical kinetics is essential to design efficient stacks. However, simulating these processes in full-stack CFD models is computationally prohibitive, especially for iterative design or real-time operation.

Recent industrial perspectives, such as those highlighted by Stargate Hydrogen [1], emphasize the need for a digital simulation approach that bridges the gap between detailed cell-level physics and stack-level performance. The vision of a stack model that incorporates cell-scale flow effects and pressure distribution into system-level analysis aligns with the growing need for digital twins in electrolyzer development.

This paper presents a modular, multiscale, and Multiphysics simulation framework that addresses these challenges. Developed in COMSOL Multiphysics®, the framework integrates high-fidelity CFD models at the cell level with reduced-order models (ROMs) to simulate and optimize stack performance. It is designed to accelerate design cycles while preserving physical fidelity by embedding cell-scale physical effects—such as gas fraction and pressure drop—into a coupled stack-scale model. This approach enables rapid evaluation of design and operational scenarios and paves the way for digital twin deployment.

2. Methodology

The simulation framework is modular and hierarchical, composed of three tightly coupled layers. Each layer reflects a different physical scale, yet all are integrated to ensure seamless propagation of relevant parameters from local to global scales.

2.1 Half-Cell CFD Models

High-resolution 3D multiphase CFD simulations are developed for both the oxygen and hydrogen half-cells. These models simulate two-phase flow, pressure drop, and gas-liquid interactions using a set of well-established configurations. The turbulence is modelled using the standard k - ϵ model with wall functions to account for near-wall effects. The gas phase is treated with a dispersed-phase approach, assuming spherical, fixed-size bubbles representative of typical gas evolution behaviour in alkaline electrolyzer. Interphase drag is modelled using the Schiller-Naumann correlation. Additional body forces such as gravity and buoyancy are included to capture realistic gas rise dynamics, while Brinkman forces are applied in porous regions to reflect flow resistance. The simulations assume isothermal operation and uniform gas generation at the electrode surfaces to simplify and focus the analysis on flow distribution and transport behaviour.

These simulations provide detailed insight into gas evolution, local resistance effects, and flow behavior that critically influence electrochemical performance. The outputs from these cell-scale models are foundational for developing the reduced-order models (ROMs) used in the manifold and stack simulations. Figure 1 illustrates the gas volume fraction distribution in the first cell of the stack. The color contour highlights regions of higher gas accumulation near the outlet, demonstrating the influence of flow path on gas-liquid distribution. This

spatial distribution of gas is a key input for evaluating local ionic resistance and voltage loss in downstream models.

Figure 1. Gas volume fraction distribution in the first cell of the stack

2.2 Manifold Reduced-Order Model

A reduced-order model (ROM) of the stack manifold is developed using parametric interpolation functions derived from the high-fidelity CFD simulations. These functions describe the relationships between flow rate and pressure drop, as well as flow rate and gas volume fraction.

Figure 2. Half cell pressure drop as a function of inlet flow rate (left), outlet gas volume fraction as a function of inlet flow rate (right)

To generate the ROM, a series of sensitivity analyses are conducted by varying the inlet flow rate and recording the corresponding flow characteristics at the half-cell level. This methodology enables the creation of accurate, data-driven models that significantly reduce computational time while maintaining fidelity. As a result, manifold performance can be evaluated under a wide range of operating conditions without the need to rerun full CFD simulations.

Figure 3. Gas volume fraction distribution in the stack manifold

The ROM is implemented in COMSOL using built-in interpolation functions, as illustrated in Figure 2, which shows the flow vs. pressure drop (left) and flow vs. gas volume fraction (right) relationships. The model facilitates the simulation of both liquid and gas distribution throughout the stack's inlet and outlet manifolds. Furthermore, it enables evaluation of critical design aspects such as electrolyte maldistribution and gas accumulation, which are essential for achieving uniform and efficient stack operation. An example of the gas volume fraction distribution in the manifold is presented in Figure 3.

2.3 Stack-Scale Electrochemical Model

The top layer of the simulation framework consists of a lumped electrochemical model that represents the entire electrolyzer stack. This model integrates the outputs from the manifold reduced-order models (ROMs), particularly the distributions of flow rate and gas volume fraction, and uses these inputs to compute local current density, cell voltage, ionic resistance, and shunt currents across the stack.

To account for performance-degrading effects such as gas-induced conductivity loss, the model applies the Bruggeman correction, which adjusts local ionic conductivity based on the gas volume fraction in each region. The spatial mapping of variables from the manifold and half-cell models is achieved through COMSOL's with-sol and general extrusion operators. These tools enable the accurate transfer of physical quantities across the different components of the simulation framework.

The resulting model allows for the identification of resistive losses caused by gas blockage and non-uniform current pathways, both of which are detrimental to stack performance. A visualization of gas volume fraction across all cells in the stack, including the inlet and outlet manifolds, is shown in Figure 4. These distributions are mapped directly from the preceding CFD and ROM-based simulations, demonstrating the integration of multiscale physical effects into the electrochemical domain.

Figure 4. Mapping of gas volume fraction distribution directly from the preceding CFD and ROM-based simulations

3. Simulation setup and initial validation

All simulations were carried out using COMSOL Multiphysics®, employing the CFD, Electrochemistry, and Multiphysics modules to capture the necessary physics and enable solution mapping across model layers. The modelled electrolyzer stack consists of seven circular cells, each 0.35 meters in diameter, connected in series and featuring single inlet and outlet manifolds on both the anode and cathode sides as shown in Figure 5. To reduce computational expense while preserving critical transport features, reduced-order models (ROMs) were constructed by conducting a series of CFD simulations across varying inlet flow rates. Interpolation functions were fitted to these results to represent key relationships, such as flow rate versus pressure drop and gas volume fraction. These ROMs were embedded into the manifold model using COMSOL's interpolation features. The coupling strategy integrates data from the CFD-based half-cell models into the manifold ROMs, whose outputs—namely flow distribution and gas phase data—are subsequently mapped into a lumped electrochemical model at the stack scale. For simplicity and consistency, all cells are assumed to be geometrically and functionally identical in the present implementation.

Figure 5: 7-cell stack geometry

As an initial step in validating the single cell model used in this framework, preliminary simulation results were benchmarked against experimental observations, as documented in

a collaborative study by Stargate Hydrogen [1]. In this validation exercise, a transparent single cell electrolyzer setup was used to visualize real-time electrolyte flow patterns through the injection of coloured dye. The CFD simulation results, which did not initially include gas evolution, closely matched the experimental images in terms of plume shape and flow dynamics as shown in Figure 6. A subsequent phase of the simulation incorporated two-phase flow by modelling gas evolution inside the cell, further increasing the fidelity and computational complexity. These simulations demonstrated realistic gas accumulation behaviour consistent with experimental expectations, particularly hydrogen stratification near the top of the cell. While this study provides a promising foundation for model credibility, further validation with full-stack experimental data is planned as part of future work.

Figure 6. Comparison of two-phase flow simulation and experimental visualization in a single electrolyzer cell. The top row shows experimental images of coloured ink (red) flow at different times, while the bottom row present corresponding simulation results. Reproduced with permission from Stargate Hydrogen [1].

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Electrochemical Performance

The simulation results demonstrate that local current distributions within the stack are strongly correlated with the gas volume fraction in the electrolyte. Elevated gas content increases ionic resistance, which in turn reduces electrochemical performance. Flow maldistribution within the inlet and outlet manifolds also contributes to non-uniform distribution of electrolyte and gas, resulting in current density hot-spots and efficiency losses. Furthermore, Shunt currents arise due to the voltage difference between the first and last cells in the stack, creating unintended current paths through the shared electrolyte channels. While these currents do not directly contribute to useful electrochemical reactions, they represent parasitic losses that reduce the overall current efficiency of the system.

Figure 7 presents 3D simulation outputs from the electrochemical model, the left image shows shunt current distribution in the manifold color-coded by voltage, while the right image displays the corresponding voltage distribution across all cells in the stack. The model facilitates detailed investigation of shunt current effects by enabling or disabling the relevant electrochemical physics or domains, thereby allowing quantitative estimation of the associated efficiency losses and supporting the development of design strategies to minimize these effects.

Figure 7. Shunt current distribution in the manifold color-coded by voltage (left) and voltage distribution across all cells in the stack (right)

4.2 Effect of Gravity

The inclusion of gravity in the multiphase CFD simulations reveals a buoyancy-driven accumulation of gas bubbles toward the top of each cell. This leads to vertical non-uniformities in gas distribution, which in turn alters both flow profiles and ionic resistance within the cell. Such gravitational effects are particularly critical for large-diameter or vertically oriented stacks, where stratification can significantly impact performance consistency.

Figure 8 illustrates these effects: the left image shows the gas volume fraction distribution in the first cell and manifold with gravity enabled, where a clear concentration of gas is observed near the outlet at the top. In contrast, the right image shows the gas distribution across the stack and manifold without gravity, representing the idealized scenario used in all other simulations in this study. These images underscore the influence of buoyancy on gas transport and support the decision to exclude gravity from the remainder of the analysis to focus on fundamental flow behavior under controlled conditions.

Figure 8. Gas volume fraction distribution in the first cell and manifold with gravity enabled (left) and across the stack and manifold without gravity

4.3 Digital Twin Relevance

The use of reduced-order models (ROMs) in the simulation framework significantly decreases computational time—by orders of magnitude—compared to full-scale CFD, making it feasible to predict stack behaviour in near real-time. The hierarchical mapping strategy enables the integration of small-scale transport phenomena, such as local gas

volume fractions and flow maldistribution, into large-scale stack models without compromising accuracy. This modelling approach establishes a robust foundation for the development of industrial digital twin systems, supporting future implementation of real-time monitoring, diagnostics, and control of alkaline electrolyzer stacks.

5. Conclusions

This paper presents a comprehensive multiscale and multiphysics simulation framework for alkaline electrolyzer stacks. By integrating detailed CFD modeling at the cell level with reduced-order models at the manifold and stack scales, the framework captures essential physical phenomena while enabling computationally efficient performance prediction. The methodology facilitates rapid design iteration, robust optimization, and paves the way for real-time digital twin deployment.

Although the framework's capabilities are demonstrated using a 7-cell industrial stack, its modularity allows adaptation to other geometries and configurations. The presented results validate the approach's accuracy and practical relevance. Future work will extend this framework to include thermal effects, electrode degradation, and real-time operational data integration.

Ultimately, this methodology supports the accelerated development and scaling of high-efficiency alkaline electrolyzer, aligning with global efforts toward sustainable hydrogen production.

References

- [1] Stargate Hydrogen Blog. Improving stack efficiency with digital simulation models. <https://stargatehydrogen.com/blog/improving-stack-efficiency/>
- [2] COMSOL Multiphysics® documentation and Application Gallery

Acknowledgement

This work was conducted as part of ENDURE; a project is supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members (grant agreement 101137925, HORIZON-JTI[1]CLEANH2-2023-1). Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Clean Hydrogen JU. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Keywords: EFCF2025, H₂, LowTemp. Fuel Cells & Electrolysers, ROM, Stack Model, Multiphysics

Remark: This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International